

Spurious suppression through the control of their couplings: application to TM cavity filters

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Abstract— In this paper, a new approach for improving filter spurious free band is proposed. The main idea is to control the coupling coefficients of the spurious resonances in order to force them to cancel each other. The required coupling levels can be estimated by using an equivalent circuit. It is observed that, in contrast with what is commonly done, it is not convenient decreasing all couplings to the spurious resonances. The only coupling to be minimized is the central one, all other should instead be maximized.

This procedure can be used for suppressing spurious resonances generated by higher order modes. This method has been here applied to TM cavity filters. As shown in the paper, it is in general applicable to even order filter only. In this paper, a two-pole TM cavity filter centered at 9 GHz with a 3 dB FBW of 1.45% has been designed and manufactured. By applying this technique, the spurious free band has been increased from 12.4 GHz of the initial design to 19.7 GHz. Measured results show the feasibility of the proposed approach.

Keywords—TM cavity, pass-band filters, coupling matrix, higher order modes, spurious resonance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pass-band filters often suffer from spurious resonances that limit the wideness of their stopband. Wider stopbands are obtained by cascading a low pass filter to a pass band filter. The advantage of having a passband filter with a wide spurious free stopband is that it allows avoiding the low pass or at least it allows using a less bulky one. Avoiding low pass filter is particularly important when bulky and heavy technologies such as waveguide technologies are used [1], especially in aerospace applications, where weight and volume reduction strongly impacts on the overall cost [2],[3].

Different techniques have been proposed for increasing the stopband. Mushroom shaped resonators, that can be also implemented in Substrate Integrated Waveguide (SIW) technology [4], can be exploited for obtaining wide stop-bands [5],[6]. In [7], wide stopband in waveguide filters is achieved by using stepped impedance resonators. A compact waveguide filter using capacitively loaded cavity with improved stopband response is proposed in [8]. Other different approaches for stopband improvement in microwave bandpass filters using microstrip and SIW technology have been reported in [9]-[12]. Another classical and intuitive approach is avoiding the excitation of the spurious resonances by setting to zero their couplings [13]. The limitation of this approach is that, in some cases, couplings can be minimized but not avoided (e.g. because of manufacturing tolerances) and this may results in stopband performance degradation.

In this work, a new technique consists in forcing the spurious resonances to cancel one another is introduced. To this end, the coupling between source (load) and spurious resonance as well as all couplings among adjacent spurious resonances (except the central coupling) are maximized. The reciprocal cancellation is obtained by minimizing just the central coupling of even order structures.

A two pole TM cavity filter has been designed and manufactured to validate the proposed idea.

II. ROUTING SCHEME INCLUDING SPURIOUS RESONANCES

Microwave and millimetre wave filters generally exploit one resonant mode (or more resonant modes in case of multimode filters) of a resonator. Unfortunately, a resonator also has higher order modes that may create undesired spurious frequencies that limit the out-of-band performances. Such spurious resonances can be taken into account in the routing scheme. An example in case of six order filter is shown in Fig. 1. In this scheme two modes for each resonator are taken into account. $R_i^{(j)}$ represent the j -th mode (with $j=1,2$) of the i -th physical cavity (with $i=1,2,3,4,5,6$). Resonant modes $R_i^{(1)}$ are exploited for generating the filter band that resonates at 9.5 GHz, whereas resonators $R_i^{(2)}$ are responsible of generating the undesired parasitic band that resonate at 10.5 GHz. Coefficients M , M_{ij} and M_c represent the normalized couplings referred to a Fractional Bandwidth (FBW) of 5%.

The classical approach for eliminating the parasitic band is to avoid the excitation of higher order modes [13]. With reference to the routing scheme of Fig. 1, this corresponds to set $M=M_c=0$. This method works in case we are able to set the couplings to zero, however in some cases we cannot guarantee that coupling values are really zero. In this case spurious may appear. This is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the response of the routing scheme of Fig. 1 is shown. The black curve represents the response when spurious coupling values are small but not zero ($M = M_c = 0.02$).

Fig. 1. Routing scheme of a filter with six resonators. In the routing scheme, the second resonance of resonators that generate a parasitic band is taken into account through an additional branch.

As can be seen, spurious appears at 10.5 GHz generating a narrow parasitic band with an insertion loss that reaches 0dB.

The new approach proposed in this paper is based on the minimization of only the central coupling M_c , whereas all other couplings M are strong. This approach allows resonances to partially cancel one another, this results in an attenuated parasitic band. This is illustrated with the red curve in Fig. 2: leaving the central coupling $M_c = 0.02$, and increasing all other couplings M to 1, an attenuation of the parasitic band of more than 23 dB is obtained. Of course, higher attenuation can be obtained for lower central coupling values, as shown by the green curve in Fig. 2 for value of $M_c=0.001$, or increasing the couplings M .

For the sake of simplicity, the proposed method has been illustrated in the case of a six order filter and with identical values of all higher order mode couplings (M) except the central one (M_c). Actually, it is not necessary to have identical coupling values, the important thing is that M_c is much smaller with respect to the others. Finally, this method is applicable to all even order filters. In other words, it is applicable to filters of order 2, 4, 6, ..., but it is not applicable to that of order 3, 5, 7, ...

Fig. 2. Response of the routing scheme of Fig. 1 for $M_{S1} = 0.55$, $M_{12} = 0.25$, $M_{23} = 0.18$, $M_{34} = 0.17$. Three different curves for different values of couplings M and M_c are plotted.

III. SECOND ORDER TM CAVITY FILTER DESIGN

TM cavity filters represent an excellent compromise when very compact structures with reasonable high Q-factors are required. The classical single mode TM cavity filter [14], is sketched in Fig. 3 together with the fundamental mode TM_{110} used for generating the pass-band, the TM_{120} undesired higher order mode generating the parasitic band and the routing scheme including the higher order modes. The cavity dimensions are $w = 23.36$, $h = 23.36$, $l = 5mm$.

In order to apply to that filter the strategy illustrated in Sec. II, the central coupling M_c should be minimized. According to Fig. 4a, this can be done by putting the central iris in a vertical position. Vertical position indeed allows maintaining the required coupling between the fundamental modes (M_{12}) but eliminate the coupling between TM_{120} modes (M_c) [15],[16]. Actually, because of the presence of the horizontal input/output irises, the TM_{120} field is perturbed and this results in a M_c small but not exactly zero. The classical theory would suggest to

zeroing all couplings, so in this case we should try to set the coupling M to zero.

Fig. 3. TM Cavity: (a) Basic structure of TM cavity; (b) Routing scheme including TM_{120} spurious modes; (c) H-field of TM_{110} ; (d) H-field for higher order TM_{120} modes.

Fig. 4. Proposed configuration for two pole TM cavity filter. (a) 3D view; (b) Frontal view.

According to the theory explained in [15],[16], this can be done by positioning the input and output horizontal irises at a distance $p = h/4 = 5.84$ mm from the centre (see fig. 4b). In [14] this degree of freedom is used to control transmission zeros. In this work instead, positioning of irises is used to improve spurious performance of the filter. With input and output irises in that position $p=h/4=5.84$ mm, $M = 0$ and M_{S1} is different from zero. However, as shown in Fig. 5, this is not the best strategy. Fig. 5a shows the frequency range of the parasitic band. As can be seen, when $p=5.84$ mm a very narrow parasitic band is obtained because of the very small couplings, however, its insertion loss reaches 0dB. Applying instead the proposed strategy that consists in increasing M , much better results are obtained. According to the theory presented in [15],[16], the coupling M can be increased by decreasing p . As shown in Fig. 5a, decreasing p the parasitic bandwidth increases, but the insertion loss become higher, and when $p = 1.8$ mm it reaches about 37 dB. Of course, once the best positioning of the irises has been established, the filter band can be designed by properly selecting the iris sizes $w1, l1, w2, l2$ in order to obtain the desired values for M_{S1} and M_{12} . Fig. 5b shows the

comparison between the filter obtained by the classical approach ($p = 5.84$ mm) and the proposed approach ($p = 1.8$ mm) in a frequency range that includes both pass-band and parasitic band. Finally, in Fig. 6 the comparison between the classical single mode TM cavity filter [14], and our version is shown. As can be seen, our version presents an impressive improvement in terms of stopband: the insertion loss is strongly increased, and the stopband increased from initial 12.4 GHz to 19.7 GHz.

Fig. 5. TM filter response. (a) response in the parasitic band range; (b) response in a wider range.

Fig. 6. Comparison between the response of the classical TM filter with all horizontally positioned irises and our filter.

Similar results can be obtained for higher (even) order filters. Preliminary results on 4-pole and 6-pole filters have already been obtained but cannot be presented here because of the lack of space. They will be presented in an expanded version of the paper.

IV. MEASUREMENTS OF THE 3D PRINTED FILTER

The designed filter has been manufactured by using a 3D printer. The filter is centred at 9 GHz and its FBW is 1.45%.

Fig. 7. Comparison between simulated and measured results together with additive manufactured photograph of the filter.

In Fig. 7, the wideband comparison between measurements and simulated results, together with the manufactured filter photograph, is shown. Because of the frequency limitation of our WR90 calibration kit, the maximum possible measured frequency is 13 GHz. Larger frequency range measurements will be done later by exploiting facilities external to our laboratory. This range is of course narrower than the whole stopband range, however this limited range already allows one to see the great improvement of the stop-band performance with respect to the classical TM mode response shown in Fig. 6.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new technique for improving the spurious performance in even order filters is illustrated. In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the method, a second order TM cavity filter with noticeable stopband performances has been designed, manufactured and measured. Very promising preliminary results have been also obtained for higher order filters and they will be presented at the conference and in an expanded paper.

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